

Section of the AGEEF	Comments
<p>Definition of AI</p> <p>1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>2. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>2.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>2.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>3. Characteristics of systems of AI</p> <p>3.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>3.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>4. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>4.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>4.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>5. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>5.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>5.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>6. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>6.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>6.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>7. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>7.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>7.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>
<p>8. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p> <p>8.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools...</p>	<p>8.1. General definition of AI as a set of tools... (repeated text from the left column)</p>

